

Design of Smart Composites Based on Shape Memory Effect

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ABSTRACT

Two types TiNi fiber reinforced composites are processed to demonstrate the effects of shape memory of TiNi fiber as temperature increases: TiNi fiber/1100 Al matrix composite and TiNi fiber/epoxy matrix composite. The yield stress of the former composite was observed to increase with prestrain at temperatures above austenitic finish temperature of TiNi fiber (A_f) while the stress intensity factor of the latter composite was reduced with prestrain at $T > A_f$. The increase in the tensile properties (yield stress and fracture toughness) was attributed to the compressive stress field in the matrix which was induced when the prestrained TiNi fibers shrink to the initial length upon heating to $T > A_f$. Analytical model is also developed to compute the compressive residual stress in the matrix, composite yield stress and stress intensity factor. The predictions based on the analytical model agree reasonably well with the experiment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Improvement of the mechanical properties (stiffness, yield stress and fracture toughness) of composites over the last decade has been modest and those of the existing composite systems decrease with an increase in temperatures despite the fact that the mechanical properties at higher temperatures are desired to be as good as at room temperature. The use of TiNi shape memory alloy (SMA) fibers for composites have been limited to control of composite structures subjected to dynamic loading.

Recently we have developed two types of smart composites where TiNi SMA fibers are used as a reinforcement and actuator to improve the mechanical properties of the composites at higher use temperatures: TiNi SMA fiber/aluminum matrix (TiNi/Al) composite [1] and TiNi SMA fiber/epoxy matrix (TiNi/epoxy) composite [2]. The former system is to enhance the tensile yield stress of the composite at higher temperatures ($> A_f$ (Austenitic finish temperature of TiNi fiber)) while the latter system is to enhance the fracture toughness of the composite at higher temperatures ($> A_f$).

The concept of enhancing the mechanical properties of the above two types of composites is schematically shown in Fig. 1. TiNi fibers are heat-treated to shape-memorize their initial length at higher temperatures ($> A_f$), then quenched to room temperature ($\approx M_s$), given prestrain

Figure 1. Design concept of smart composite

Figure 2. As-processed TiNi/Al composite

Figure 3. Mechanical behavior of TiNi fiber at different temperatures:
 (a) strain vs. temperature under a constant stress $\sigma = 93.7$ MPa
 (b) stress-strain curves at different temperatures

$\epsilon_T (>0)$ and embedded in the matrix material to form a composite. The composite is then heated to temperatures ($>A_f$) at which the TiNi fibers tend to shrink back to their initial length by the amount of prestrain ϵ_T without the constraint of the matrix material. This induces the tensile stress in the TiNi fibers, but the matrix is subjected to compressive stress. It is this compressive stress in the matrix that contributes to the enhancement of the tensile properties of the composite (yield stress and flow stress) and fracture toughness.

Experimental procedure and results are stated in Section 2, and the analytical modeling in Section 3. Then discussion is given in Section 4, followed by conclusion in Section 5.

2. EXPERIMENT

Experimental work was conducted on two different TiNi composite: TiNi/Al metal matrix composite and TiNi/epoxy polymer matrix composite. Processing, mechanical testing and experimental results of each composite system will be described briefly below.

2.1. TiNi/Al COMPOSITE

TiNi fibers (Ti-50.2% at Ni) of 200 μm diameter supplied by Kantoc Ltd, Fujisawa, Japan in form of continuous fibers, are cut into short fibers of given length and they are arranged into a mold where the top and bottom plates are perforated by a laser beam. Molten aluminum (99.7% purity) is then poured into the mold with TiNi fibers and then squeeze-casted at 970K and 65MPa. Two different volume fractions of fiber (f) are used to process the composite: $f=0.04$ and 0.09. Unreinforced aluminum specimen was also processed by the same processing route. The cross-sectional view of a as-processed TiNi/Al composite is shown in Fig. 2. Tensile specimen of flat bar type with gauge length 30 mm and thickness 2 mm are made from as-processed TiNi/Al ingot by electro discharge machining.

In order to determine the transformation temperatures and stress-strain relations of TiNi fiber, we conducted tensile testing on TiNi fiber at different temperatures (T). The results are summarized in Fig. 3 where (a) and (b) denote the strain- T relation and stress-strain curves at constant temperature: $T=20, 40, 60, 80$ and 100°C . From Fig. 3(a), one can obtain four transformation temperatures of TiNi fiber: Martensitic start (M_s), Martensitic finish (M_f), Austenitic start (A_s) and Austenitic finish (A_f). Hence $M_s=31^\circ\text{C}$, $M_f=15^\circ\text{C}$, $A_s=57^\circ\text{C}$, $A_f=63^\circ\text{C}$.

Next TiNi/Al composite specimens are first shape memorized by subjecting them to 500°C for 1 hr, followed by quenching to ice-water temperature. The TiNi/Al specimens with and without prestrain (ϵ_T) at room temperature are subjected to tensile testing at 90°C to study the shape memory effect. The results are shown in Fig. 4 which demonstrates the enhanced tensile properties (yield and flow stress) of the composite with prestrain 4% as compared with the composite without prestrain. The increase in the observed tensile properties of TiNi/Al composite with prestrain will be compared with the predictions based on the analytical model (Section 3) and the results given in Section 4.

2.2 TiNi/EPOXY COMPOSITE

The shape-memorized TiNi fibers are arranged in a mold to which photoelastic epoxy and specified amount of hardener (both supplied by Chiba Geigy) are poured and then kept a 130°C for 2 hours for curing. After curing, as-molded composite is cooled to room temperature. During the process, TiNi fibers are kept in tension with a given prestrain. A side notch of length 4 mm is then cut into the as-molded composite specimen. The geometry of the composite specimen is shown in Fig. 5 from which the volume fraction of the TiNi fibers is calculated as $f=0.094$.

A constant load of 300N is applied to the composite with the side notch. The number of fringe pattern lines developed around the notch tip in the composite is measured under different

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves of TiNi/Al composite with and without prestrain and unreinforced Al at 80°C

Figure 5. Geometry of TiNi/epoxy composite specimen with a side notch

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 6. Fringe patterns around the side notch of TiNi/epoxy specimen loaded by 300N at 80°C with different prestrains: (a) 0%, (b) 1%, (c) 3% and (d) 5%

constant temperatures. The results of the photoelasticity experiment are shown in Fig. 6 where (a), (b), (c) and (d) denote the fringe pattern developed around the notch tip in the composite with prestrain 0, 1, 3 and 5% tested at 80°C, respectively. Fig. 6 demonstrates clearly the shape memory effect as the stress intensity factor measured at 80°C ($>A_f$) is reduced with increasing prestrain. Stress intensity factor K_I can be computed from

$$K_I = \frac{n\sqrt{2}\pi r_m}{\alpha t \sin \theta_m} \left[1 + \left(\frac{2}{3 \tan \theta_m} \right)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \left[1 + \frac{2 \tan(3\theta_m/2)}{3 \tan \theta_m} \right] \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of the fringe, t is the composite plate thickness, α is the epoxy photoelasticity sensitivity constant, r_m and θ_m are, respectively, the distance and angle in polar coordinates at point M , shown schematically in Fig. 7. The results of the reduction in the stress intensity factor ΔK_I of the composite are plotted as a function of prestrain in Fig. 8 where the predictions by the analytical model are also shown.

Figure 7. Fringe pattern developed in front of a crack size a

Figure 8. Stress intensity factor change ΔK_I of side notched TiNi/epoxy composite vs. prestrain

3. ANALYTICAL MODELING

Analytical modeling consists of three steps: (1) computation of the compressive residual stress in the matrix (2) prediction of composite yield stress and (3) prediction of ΔK_I .

3.1. RESIDUAL STRESS

We are concerned with the residual stress field in a TiNi composite when prestrained TiNi fibers with its amount ϵ_T shrink back to its initial length under the martensitic to austenitic transformation which can take place upon heating to $T (>A_f)$. When ϵ_T is large which is the case with the present study, either fiber or matrix can yield. It was found in our previous analysis [3] that the matrix yielding occurs if

$$\frac{(1-f)}{f} \sigma_{ym} < \sigma_{yf} \quad (2)$$

while the fiber can yield if

$$\frac{(1-f)}{f} \sigma_{ym} > \sigma_{yf} \quad (3)$$

where σ_{ym} and σ_{yf} are the yield stress of the matrix and fiber, respectively. Following Eshelby's equivalent inclusion method [4, 5], the stress in the fiber can be expressed as

$$\underline{\sigma}_f = C_f \cdot (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}_T - \mathbf{e}_p) = C_m \cdot (\mathbf{e} - \mathbf{e}^*) \quad (4)$$

where C_f and C_m are the stiffness tensors of the fiber and matrix, \mathbf{e} the induced strain, \mathbf{e}_T the transformation strain, \mathbf{e}_p the plastic strain of the fiber if Eqn. (3) is satisfied, or $-\mathbf{e}_p$ where \mathbf{e}_p is the matrix plastic strain if Eqn. (2) is satisfied, \mathbf{e}^* is the eigenstrain fictitiously introduced to the fiber domain and unknown to be solved, and it is related to \mathbf{e} by

$$\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{e}^* \quad (5)$$

and where \mathbf{S} is the Eshelby tensor.

Once the fiber stress $\underline{\sigma}_f$ is computed, the average matrix stress $\underline{\sigma}_m$ can be obtained from the equilibrium equation of force:

$$(1-f)\underline{\sigma}_m + f\underline{\sigma}_f = 0 \quad (6)$$

It is noted in the above equations that the stress ($\underline{\sigma}$) and strain field (\mathbf{e}) are tensorial, thus having six independent components. However, due to axisymmetry, only independent components are 11 (=22) and 33 where the fiber axis is taken along the x_3 -axis. Thus, the components of the fiber transformation strain \mathbf{e}_T are given by

$$\mathbf{e}_T = (v_f \mathbf{e}_T, v_f \mathbf{e}_T, -\mathbf{e}_T, 0, 0, 0) \quad (7)$$

where $-\mathbf{e}_T$ in Eqn. (7) is the shrinkage strain whose magnitude is assumed to be equal to prestrain and v_f is the fiber's Poisson's ratio.

3.2 COMPOSITE YIELD STRESS

The analytical model for prediction of the composite yield stress has been developed elsewhere [3], thus a brief summary is given here. Assuming uniform plastic strain in the matrix \mathbf{e}_p ($-\mathbf{e}_p/2, -\mathbf{e}_p/2, \mathbf{e}_p, 0, 0, 0$), developed under applied stress $\underline{\sigma}_0$, one can compute the fiber stress $\underline{\sigma}_f$ by using the Eshelby's model. The change in the total potential energy due to small change in \mathbf{e}_p , $\delta \mathbf{e}_p$, δU plus the plastic work in the matrix due to $\delta \mathbf{e}_p$ must be equal to zero, resulting in

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_{ym} + \frac{f}{1-f} (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})_f \quad (8)$$

where σ_0 is the applied stress along the x_3 -axis, σ_{33} , σ_{11} are the fiber stress along the x_3 -axis, and x_1 -axis, respectively. After substituting the results of fiber stress components, Eqn. (8) is reduced to

$$\sigma_0 = Y \sigma_{ym} + H \mathbf{e}_p \quad (9)$$

where Y is the non-dimensional factor and larger than 1 and function of the properties of the matrix and fibers as well as f , and H is the work hardening rate.

3.3 REDUCTION IN STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR DUE TO PRESTRAIN AND SHAPE MEMORY EFFECT

When a crack tip is subjected to compressive stress q , then the change in the stress intensity ΔK_I is given by [6]

$$\Delta K_I = 2q\sqrt{\frac{2D}{\pi}} \quad (10)$$

where D is the length of the compressive stress domain. Eqn. (10) was originally formulated by Tada et al. has been used by several researchers [7, 8]. Taya et al. [8] recently applied the above model to assess the toughening by thermal residual stress in TiB_2 particulate/SiC matrix composite where compressive stress in SiC matrix is induced, thus reducing the stress intensity factor which is equivalent to the increase in the fracture toughness ΔK_{IC} . The value of D in the present experiment is 1 mm, see Fig. 5, thus Eqn. (10) is rewritten as

$$\Delta K_I = 0.05q\sqrt{m} \quad (11)$$

where q is in unit of MPa, and computed from the residual stress model discussed in subsection 3.1. The predicted results of ΔK_I are plotted as open circle in Fig. 8.

4. DISCUSSION

The analytical results based on the preceding models are used to compute the composite yield stress of TiNi/Al composite and the change in the stress intensity factor ΔK_I of TiNi/epoxy composite. The input data for these computations are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of constituents

Material	Young's modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Yield stress (MPa)
Al	69	0.34	33
epoxy	6	0.39	25
TiNi fiber	82	0.43	500

The stress-strain curve of TiNi exhibits a non-linear work-hardening type behavior as seen in Fig. 3(b). This non-linear plastic region is pseudo-plastic since the microscopic level relaxation of TiNi fiber is the twinning induced by stress (stress induced martensites).

4.1 YIELD STRESS OF TiNi/Al COMPOSITE

The residual stresses in the composite and the composite yield stress are computed by the present models and the results are given in Table 2 where the experimental results of the composite yield stress are also given as marked with *.

Table 2. Residual stresses and yield stress of the TiNi/Al composite with prestrain 4%
* experimental data

Volume fraction of fiber (f)	Matrix stresses		Fiber stresses		Composite Yield stress (MPa)
	$\sigma_{11}=\sigma_{22}$ (MPa)	σ_{33} (MPa)	$\sigma_{11}=\sigma_{22}$ (MPa)	σ_{33} (MPa)	
0.04	-4.3	-25.1	102.1	602.1	52.4 *50.0
0.09	-10.0	-42.5	100.7	429.3	67.0 *70.0

It can be concluded from Fig. 4 and Table 2 that the prestrain given to the TiNi fiber gives rise to the compressive stress in the matrix which in turn increases the composite yield stress, and the analytical model can explain the experiment reasonably well.

4.2 ΔK_I OF TiNi/EPOXY COMPOSITE

Both experimental and predicted results of the reduction in the stress concentration factor ΔK_I of TiNi/epoxy composite are shown in Fig. 8. As to the ΔK_I -prestrain relation, the analytical model explains the same trend as the experimental results, i.e., $|\Delta K_I|$ decreases with increase in prestrain. The reason for the predictions being larger than the experiment is: The strain induced during the epoxy curing was not accounted for in the analytical model. If this was considered, the effective transformation strain should be reduced by the amount of the cure strain, thus making the predictions closer agreement with the experiment.

5. CONCLUSION

Shape memory effect of TiNi fiber upon temperature increase was utilized to design two types of TiNi composite with given prestrain (ϵ_T) whose tensile properties (yield stress and fracture toughness) increase with ϵ_T .

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